

SYNOPSIS
DOCTOR OF SCIENCE (D.Sc.)

Post-doctorate Research Programme in Medical Biochemistry

ASSESSING NUTRITIONAL STATUS OF CHILDREN
IN PRESCHOOL AGE

Submitted by

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INTRODUCTION

Applied Biochemistry deals with the basic concepts and practically oriented facts of biochemistry which are valuable in understanding the health and diseases among humans, assessing the impact of nutritional deficiency on the health of children, investigation of community health, improvement in the yield of crops, betterment in the pest control strategies for the benefit of humans.

Research focuses on the cognitive ability of individuals towards the systematic investigation and substantiating the prevalent facts, concepts and phenomena or to establish the innovation for the advancement of knowledge (Creswell 2008). Practically, the scientific study concentrates upon defining and redefining the research problem; formulating the hypothesis; collecting, summarizing and analyzing the data; drawing the inferences and testing them to find out whether inferences fit the formulated hypothesis. The primary outcome of the study is not easy to frame and is dependent upon the streams that are related to the study. Generally, the study can be classified into two main streams as pure research and applied research. Furthermore, every research study is helpful in understanding thoroughly the problems, issues and concerns of the society for the betterment of mankind.

Nutritional status exemplifies the health of the individual that is controlled by the intake and utilization of nutrients by the individual (Beaton 1986). It depends on the intake of balanced diet accompanied by its absorption and assimilation in the human body. Moreover, nutritional status of the individual refers to the utmost necessity of the healthy body which is maintained by sufficient intake of nutrition and adequate level of nutrients in the body. Furthermore, nutritional status conveys the dynamic physiological state of the individual arises from the balance between the need of nutrients and their consumption together their normal absorption and assimilation in the body.

Assessment of the nutritional status yields diagnostic tools to the dieticians and clinicians in understanding health and diseases of humans. It portrays substantive prognostic ability in predicting the morbidity, survival, and mortality of children and adults (Block 1982).

The nutritional status assessment involves many steps. The essential step in nutritional assessment is the use of anthropometric parameters that involves the measurement of baseline height, weight, and mid-arm circumference of the children (WHO 2019).

The successive record of alteration in these parameters, history of change in weight, dietary schedule are the practical findings which are helpful in the diagnosis of diseases and also predict the prognosis of diseases (Arrieta 2010). Furthermore, assessment of nutritional status encloses additional dimensions as biochemical indices, clinical parameters, and dietary indices.

The biochemical indices comprise assessment of serum globulin, serum albumin, serum total proteins, hemoglobin concentration, RBCs count, level of serum electrolytes, plasma vitamins concentration, plasma iron concentration, serum total iron binding capacity, lipid profile, liver function tests and renal function tests to forecast the nutritional disorders and health of children and adults.

The clinical parameters of nutritional status assessment includes exhaustive past medical history, general physical examination, history of diarrhoea episodes, history of drug allergy, history of nutritional supplements, history of upper respiratory tract infection, and history of abnormal habit as clay eating so as to decode clinical manifestations of malnutrition in children (Kondrup 2003).

The dietary indices nutritional status assessment involves daily need of nutrients, intake of sufficient amount and good quality of nutrients, history of allergy to foods, and intolerance to particular food item that fundamentally help to comprehend the dietary need and diseases of children and adults and additionally, yields substantive knowledge in the selection of food from food groups and planning of balanced diet (Payette 2000).

The assessment of the nutritional status of children is the grey area for the research scholars. It is recommended that the national nutritional status assessment programme should be prepared, propagated and linked with the routine laboratory tests.

The impaired nutritional status conveys state of malnutrition in children. This is a broad concept that signifies deviation from the normal nutritional health status which could be either undernutrition or overnutrition or the deficiency of minerals in the body (UNCF 2010).

Both the terms as undernutrition and malnutrition are synonymously used in the stream nutritional biochemistry to describe an impaired state of nutritional health of the affected children and adults. **The chief predisposing factor of malnutrition is the aberrant dietary habit of the affected individual that leads to either consumption of large amount of food beyond the recommended dietary allowance, or intake of large quantity of carbohydrate rich and fatty foods (Overnutrition) (UNCF 2010), or consumption of insufficient amount**

and poor quality foods that are deficient of macronutrients and electrolytes (Undernutrition) (UNCF 2010).

Moreover, **the overnutrition and undernutrition are prevalent as comorbidity in the developing countries in entirely separate community.** The overnutrition is predominantly found in the children of upper socioeconomic zones, whereas, the undernutrition is prevalent commonly among the children of lower socioeconomic zones. The coexistence of overnutrition and undernutrition in the subset populations is referred as double burden of malnutrition.

Preschool children belong to an age range between 2 years to below 5 years as described by academicians and scientists. In the preschool age, the children are educated through skills as the administration of story books, toys, comic books. In this age group, children are imparted training for social relations.

Stunting represents the growth disorder which is clinically manifested as the compromised growth and weakened development of the children in the developmental age due to either malnutrition, or occurrence of infection, or impaired cognitive behavior (Gupta 2017a;WHO 2010). The stunting is referred as the clinical condition described by measurement of anthropometric index as height-for-age of the child below ($<-2SD$) from the median of the WHO Child Growth Standards (WHO 2006).

Stunting is the discrepancy in linear growth of the child. It represents a state of chronic malnutrition (WHO 2006). Stunting is the significant biomarker of the nutritional status of the children showing its comorbidity with the mortality and morbidity in children. Stunting is related to the development of intelligence, cognitive function, sensorimotor reflexes, and health of the children in the adolescent period of life (WHO 2010).

Malnutrition is the clinical manifestation owing to consumption of either insufficient food or excessive food. **The World Health Organization declares malnutrition as the major public health hazard.** The prevalence of under-nutrition in the children in preschool age is growing in developing countries.

Wasting is a type of acute malnutrition. It is referred as the weight-for-age of child below ($<-2SD$) from the median of the WHO child growth standards (WHO 2006; WHO 2010).

Wasting results owing to either decreased intake of calories that is inadequate to maintain normal growth and development or the wastage of nutrients from the body owing to acute infection or the comorbidity of the two conditions interacting in a viciously (WHO 2010).

Malnourished children suffer from compromised immune status and raised predilection to episodes of diarrhoea, acute upper respiratory tract infection, viral infections and tuberculosis.

Dental caries is the chronic and progressive microbial disease affecting hard tissues of teeth. It is characterized initially by decalcification of enamel, dentine and cementum of affected teeth followed by degradation of organic solids of the teeth. **Early childhood dental caries** is the age specific dental disease in preschool aged children which is the chronic form of infection. It affects the deciduous teeth of children. It is the significant dental health hazard among children in developmental years of life (Chakraborty 1997).

The oro-dental health of the preschool children is the issue of special concern for the parents in the developed countries and in the urban population in the developing countries.

The Dunning, 1986, posited the intimate relation between the dental and the general health of children.

The preschool children suffering from early childhood caries exhibit anxious behavior. It affects the appetite, growth and development of the involved children. The relation dental health and general health is established (Grossi and Genco 1998). The disorders like diabetes mellitus and cardiovascular disease have significant oro-dental complications.

Anemia is the clinical disorder characterized by decreased RBC's count and or reduced level of hemoglobin in the red blood cells in comparison to the reference value (Gupta (2015). The nutritional anemia clinically manifests owing to dietary deficiency of electrolytes as iron, folic acid, cyanocobalamine, or the composite result into reduction in hemoglobin concentration and erythrocytic count in the body. The nutritional anemia is the major health hazard that affects the population of preschool children, pregnant women and women in lactation in developed as well as developing countries (Gupta 2017b).

Prevalence of iron deficiency anemia contributes about 50% of the total child affected with anemia though the world. Clinical sign of pallor is the significant sign of anemia which is manifested in the form as yellow discoloration of the skin, mucosa, conjunctiva, nail beds, and palm. It is the important clinical index for anemia especially screening patients in the distant areas in which medical and paramedical facilities are not adequate. Pallor has incredible sensitivity to detect iron deficiency anemia from mild to moderate severity in primary health care centers (Gupta 2017a). Additionally, diagnosis of anemia through clinical sign of pallor has substantive clinical value where medical laboratory setting is poor.

Clay eating (geophagia) in the human population has been prevalent since prehistoric period. Geophagia is a type of Pica. The word has its root in the Latin that conveys “Magpie” which is a bird having persistent eating habit. As per the American Psychiatric Association, geophagia is the strong urge for eating non-nutritive substances like clay, chalk, soil and chips from the walls (Gupta 2019).

Geophagy is designated as the global public health problem which is related to innumerable etiological factors as culture, micronutrient deficiency, psychological stress, psychiatric behavior and adaptive behavior (Gupta 2019). The scientists all over the world are ambiguous about the universalization of the causes, pathogenesis and treatment measures concerning geophagia.

Geophagia exerts deleterious effects on the affected population ranging from helminthes infestation, malabsorption syndrome, poor appetite, stunted growth and diarrhoea (Gupta 2015).

RATIONALE

Nutritional health of preschool children as wasting, stunting, anemia; public health as diarrhoea, geophagia and dental caries negatively affect the physical, mental and intellectual health of preschool children under the age of five years. The children in the formative years of age require adequate nutrition, clean drinking water, proper sanitation, adequate hygiene, sound psychosocial interactions, parental care, and medical facility for proper growth and development; normal sensorimotor reflexes, cognitive capability, and intellectual ability to lead a healthy life.

Prevalence of nutritional status, public health and general health is thoroughly documented at the national and international levels. Moreover, scarce data is accessible specific to a region and locality. Therefore, present study will be conducted to assess prevalence of nutritional status, public health and general health in children between 2 years to below 5 years of age in the city, Fazilka in Punjab.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Nutritional health, public health and dental health of children are interlinked. The concepts and practical knowledge of biochemistry are applied towards understanding the health and diseases of children between 2 years to below 5 years of age

SCOPE OF STUDY

The present study will embark upon the use of practical concepts of biochemistry like anthropometric parameters to decode the nutritional status of children. The practical knowledge of dental biochemistry will help to find out the dental health and its association with general health of children. The biochemical markers in the present study will delineate the etiology of geophagia among children and pregnant women and to integrate the habit of geophagia with general health of the individuals.

PRIMARY OUTCOME

Present study will provide data concerning the prevalence of stunting, wasting, dental caries, diarrhoea, geophagia in a population of children between 2 years to below 5 years of age

SECONDARY OUTCOME

The study will yield data regarding correlation of nutritional status of children with prevalence of diarrhoea, geophagia and dental caries

LIMITATIONS OF STUDY

The present study will be limited to children between 2 years to below 5 years of age. The study will be confined to the city, Fazilka in Punjab. The study will not assess invasive biochemical biomarkers. The study will not assess the incidence of nutritional status, public and dental health of children.

AIM OF STUDY

The present study will be focused at exploring the role of applied biochemistry in assessing the nutritional health, public health and dental health of children between 2 years to below 5 years of age group.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

Present study will serve to fulfill following objectives as:

1. To find out the prevalence of stunting and wasting in children between 2 years to below 5 years of age group.
2. To assess the prevalence of anemia in children between 2 years to below 5 years of age group.
3. To find out the prevalence of diarrhoea in children between 2 years to below 5 years of age group.
4. To assess the prevalence of dental caries in children between 2 years to below 5 years of age group.
5. To find out the prevalence of geophagia in children between 2 years to below 5 years of age group.
6. To find out the association between stunting and wasting with diarrhoea children between 2 years to below 5 years of age group.
7. To assess the association between stunting and wasting with anemia in children between 2 years to below 5 years of age group.
8. To assess the association between stunting and wasting with geophagia in children between 2 years to below 5 years of age group.
9. To find out the relation among stunting, wasting, age and gender of children between 2 years to below 5 years of age group.
10. To assess the prevalence of dental caries and its association with stunting, wasting, anemia and diarrhoea in children between 2 years to below 5 years of age group.

HYPOTHESES OF STUDY

1. There would be significant prevalence of stunting and wasting in children between 2 years to below 5 years of age group.

2. There would be significant prevalence of anemia in children between 2 years to below 5 years of age group.
3. There would be present significant prevalence of diarrhoea in children between 2 years to below 5 years of age group.
4. There would be significant prevalence of dental caries in children between 2 years to below 5 years of age group.
5. There would be significant prevalence of geophagia in children between 2 years to below 5 years of age group.
6. The stunting and wasting would be significantly associated with diarrhoea in children between 2 years to below 5 years of age group.
7. The stunting and wasting would be significantly associated with anemia in children between 2 years to below 5 years of age group.
8. The stunting and wasting would be significantly associated with geophagia in children between 2 years to below 5 years of age group.
9. There would be significant association among stunting, wasting, age and gender of children between 2 years to below 5 years of age.
10. There would be significant association among dental caries, stunting, wasting, anemia and diarrhoea in children between 2 years to below 5 years of age group.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH DESIGN

Prospective, observational, descriptive, and cross-sectional research design would be adopted for present study.

SAMPLING DESIGN

Study area

Present study will be conducted in the city, Fazilka located in Punjab state in India. The Fazilka city is situated on Indo-Pak border in the state of Punjab in India. According to Census of India, 2011, the Fazilka city has a population of 67,424, comprising nearly 52% males and 48% females. The 13% of the population is represented by children below 6 years of age.

Sample frame and Sampling units

The child population between 2 years to below 5 years of age residing in the Fazilka city will constitute sample frame. The children who qualify the sample selection criteria will be the considered as the sampling units.

Sample Selection Criteria

Inclusion Criteria

- ✓ Children between 2 years and below 5 years of age group
- ✓ Children residing in the city, Fazilka in Punjab state in India
- ✓ Girls and boys will be eligible for study

Exclusion Criteria

- ✓ Children who will be either under 2 years of age and/or above 5 years of age
- ✓ Children who will be severely ill
- ✓ Children who will be apprehensive and crying at the time of examination will be excluded from the study

Sample Selection Method

Random, two-stage cluster sampling method will be adopted

In the first stage, the Fazilka city will be grouped into three strata, as:

- ✓ Elementary schools
- ✓ Childcare centers (Anganwadi)
- ✓ Slum areas

A sample frame of elementary schools, childcare centers, and slum areas will be prepared. A population of 30% of elementary schools, child care centers and slum areas will be selected randomly from the sample frame.

In the second stage, all the children (clusture) who will fulfill sample selection criteria will be selected for the study.

Sample Size Determination

Sample size will be determined on the basis of following formula, as:

Sample size formula

$$(n) = Z^2 \times p \times q/d^2$$

Z=A value of 1.96 will be substituted at 95% confidence interval

P =A prevalence of 47% of malnutrition will be substituted in the formula

q =(1-p)

d=5% margin of error

After calculation of sample size by the formula, a non-response rate of 15% will be added
Therefore, after final adjustment, sample size (N=440) will be selected

DATA COLLECTION DESIGN

Type of Data

- ✓ Primary data will be collected in the present study

Data Collection Instruments

- ✓ The observation and interview schedules will be utilized for recording demographic characteristics, anthropometric measurement and clinical signs of participants

Data Collection Techniques

Direct Observation and Interview methods

The methods will be used to extract data regarding demographic characteristics, habit of geophagia, episodes of diarrhea (number of diarrheal episodes 2 weeks prior to investigation)

Inspection method:

The method will be used to extract data concerning anemia, dental caries after inspection of conjunctiva, nail beds and teeth of children

Anthropometric measurements

- ✓ The height of participants will be measured utilizing a vertical wooden height board. The children will be kept on board. The posture of children will be maintained straight and upright in the middle of the board. The body parts of children as head, shoulders, buttocks, knees, and heels should touch the board. The height will be recorded in centimeter units
- ✓ The weight will be measured utilizing a weighing balance. The balance will be calibrated every time intervening two measurement of two children. The child will be asked to stand barefooted on the balance. The light clothing of children will be preferred while recording weight. It will be recorded in kilogram units.

Data Collection Scales

- ✓ Interval scale will be utilized for recording age, weight, and height of children
- ✓ The characteristics like stunting, pallor, geophagy, illiteracy, monthly income, and diarrheal episode will be in terms of prevalence.

Prevalence of a variableNumber of participants affected

Total number of participants × 100

Cut offs

- ✓ Height for age and weight for height of the participants will be expressed in standard deviation recommended by the WHO
- ✓ The WHO standard deviation (<-2SD) will be implied as cutoff for defining wasting and stunting among participants
- ✓ Pallor in conjunctiva and nail beds will be the qualitative cutoff for determination of anemia in participants
- ✓ Presence of CATCH on the surfaces of teeth by instrument shall be a cutoff for determination of dental caries

- ✓ Frequency of diarrheal episodes as reported by the parents/teachers/guardians of participants 2 weeks prior to the visit of investigation team shall be a cutoff mark for the determination of diarrhea
- ✓ Reporting by the parents/teachers/guardians of participants about the intake of clay by (irrespective of the frequency) participants shall be the cutoff for determination of habit of geophagia

Study Variables

Dependent variable

- ✓ Stunting
- ✓ Wasting
- ✓ Anemia
- ✓ Geophagia
- ✓ Diarrhoea
- ✓ Dental caries

Independent variables:

- ✓ Age
- ✓ Gender
- ✓ Elementary school, childcare center, and slum area
- ✓ Income of household per month
- ✓ Illiteracy

STATISTICAL DESIGN

Descriptive analysis

- ✓ The collected data will be summarized into tables
- ✓ The study variables will be mentioned in terms of frequency (n/N), percentage (n%), and prevalence

Correlation analysis

- ✓ Odd ratio will be computed with 95% confidence interval (CI)

Inferential analysis

- ✓ Hypothesis testing will be done by Chi-square test for independence
- ✓ $p \leq 0.05$ will be implied as statistically significant for all tests

ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

The approval for the present study will be taken from the principal of institution as well as managing committee members

CONSENT

The study goals will be narrated to parents/teachers/guardians of the participants. The Oral consent will be procured. The data will be kept confidential to maintain identity of the participants

IMPLICATIONS OF STUDY

- ✓ Present study would intercept the prevalence of malnutrition in terms of wasting and stunting in children below age of five years in the city Fazilka in Punjab
- ✓ Present study would affect the prevalence of diarrhoea in children below age of five years in the city Fazilka in Punjab
- ✓ The study would deliver information about the anemia in children below age of five years in the city Fazilka in Punjab and will help the
- ✓ Study would provide remedial measures to intercept the vicious cycle between diarrhoea and wasting
- ✓ Present study would provide information about the malnutrition and dental caries
- ✓ Study would explain comorbidity of nutritional anemia and geophagia

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